

ADAPTATION OF DEVELOPING TENDON-TO-BONE INSERTION SITE TO OPTIMIZE STRESS ENVIRONMENT

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1 Introduction

The concepts of adaptive materials and functionally graded composites have been developed for the last three decades. However, nature has “employed” the same concepts for millions of years. The realization that invaluable lessons can be learned from nature generated an interest in biomimetics. The branch of biomimetics concerned with the evaluation of biological systems and application of the acquired knowledge to improve surgical and healing protocols has also gained broad acceptance.

The tendon-to-bone attachment (enthesis or insertion site) represents an amazing example of a reliable joint between two dissimilar materials with almost two orders of magnitude difference in the stiffness (elastic modulus of bone is about 20 GPA, while the longitudinal and transverse moduli of tendon are of an order of 450 MPa and 45 MPa, respectively). This abrupt change occurs along a very small distance that is less than 1 mm in humans and much smaller in such animals as mice. It is recognized that the optimum stiffness distribution resulting in the resilient enthesis possessing high strength is achieved through several mechanisms [1]: (1) orientation of collagen (protein) fibers; (2) gradual variation of mineral deposits on these fibers from a continuous sheath near bone to the bound of the mineralized region of enthesis; (3) interdigitation of bone and tendon at the interface; (4) morphology, i.e. the optimum shape of enthesis reducing local stress concentrations at the junction with bone; (5) attachment angle between enthesis and bone.

It has long been realized that a mature bone adapts its mass and architecture to external mechanical loads [2], increasing the bone density in response to physical activity [3] and decreasing it in the absence of such activity [4]. The strength of the tendon is also positively affected by the activity level

[5], [6]. A reduced load deteriorates the development of the tendon-to-bone insertion site, reducing its stiffness, strength, and mineral content [7].

Accordingly, it seems to be counterintuitive that the enthesis can develop under very low mechanical stresses in the early post-natal phase of life. We addressed this question specifying and tracing biology of the enthesis during the post-natal development and employing this data in our analysis. Our experimental [8], analytical and numerical studies outlined in this paper demonstrate that even though the applied mechanical force is very low, the post-natal insertion site experiences an accumulation of mineral and undergoes the desirable development as a result of high stress concentrations at both tissue and cell levels.

2 Analysis

2.1. Problem formulation and approach

The effect of mineral grading from the front of the mineralized fibrocartilage to the bone on the distribution of mechanical properties and stresses in the enthesis has been discussed in our previous studies [9], [10]. In particular, we investigated the pattern of the mineralization in the collagen fibrils that form the fibers. Each fibril consists of triple-helix collagen molecules arranged in the staggered array. In a partially mineralized section of the enthesis the gaps between the molecules are filled with mineral platelets. Upon further mineralization, mineral sheath develops on the outer surface of the fibril. The distribution of the stiffness in a mature enthesis was modeled using FEA accounting for a gradual accumulation of the mineral inside and on the surface of collagen fibrils. The sequence of such accumulation from the front of the mineralized

fibrocartilage to the bone, beginning with platelets filling the gaps within the fibril, eventually followed with a random-pattern formation of the sheath on the surface of the fibril is discussed in detail in [9]. The resulting distribution of the longitudinal and transverse moduli of mineralized collagen tissue with respect to the mineral volume fraction based on the nanoscale details of the accumulation of mineral within and on the surface of collagen fibrils is shown in Fig. 1.

The question we considered in the present study was related to the formation of the mineralized fibrocartilage tissue in the post-natal phase. While it is recognized that the mineralization of the part of tendon adjacent to bone occurs under stresses, we know that soon after birth mechanical stresses in the tissue are very low. Therefore, we have to question the feasibility of and the trigger for the development of mineral in the post-natal enthesis. One plausible explanation would be the presence of high stress concentration conducive for local mineral formation. However, we observed that the mineral gradient at the enthesis is present from the early phase of the development. Judging by the experience for mature enthesis, such gradient should reduce local stress concentrations, i.e. to be counterproductive for the mineral formation. Accordingly, it is plausible that the gradient serves a different function during the development post-natal phase of life that is not related to a reduction of local stresses.

Our research confirmed earlier findings indicating the presence of chondrocyte cells in the tissue immediately after birth. These cells facilitating the formation of minerals experience transformations, eventually being replaced with osteoblasts and a fully mineralized collagen (protein) matrix. In experiments [8] we observed that the mineral gradient at the boundary of mineralized and non-mineralized fibrocartilage develops at the early post-natal phase and remains unchanged during the development. Accordingly, our assumption was that the presence of mineral at the early life phase produces local cell-scale stress concentration around mineralized chondrocytes (cells that are present after birth but gradually diminish in size in a mature organism). The unit cell analyzed to specify the stress concentration at the cell scale is shown in Fig. 2.

We applied the empirical morphological data to generate tissue-scale and cell-scale enthesis models throughout the postnatal period of mice, from 7 to 56 days after birth. The analytical models employed in the analysis reflected the axisymmetry in the rotator cuff tendon insertion at both tissue and cell scales as demonstrated in Fig. 2.

The use of fifteen CD1 mice for this study was approved by the animal studies committee at Washington University. Mice were sacrificed in a CO₂ chamber at 7, 10, 14, 28, and 56 days after birth. The humerus and supraspinatus tendon with muscle attached were dissected free of all other tissues. Two dimensional sagittal plane images were acquired using a micro-computed tomography scanner.

The shoulder specimens used were rehydrated and decalcified using 14% EDTA for two weeks. Samples were dehydrated, embedded in paraffin, and sectioned in the coronal plane. Tissue sections were stained with toluidine blue to estimate extracellular matrix area fraction. To calculate the approximate matrix area fraction, we analyzed images using ImageJ software. The humeral head diameter was determined by calibrating ImageJ to a scale bar to measure the widest diameter of the humeral head on the section. Tendon length was measured using ImageJ from the insertion to the beginning of muscle (see [8] for further details). As a result of these experiments, we were able to monitor the volume fraction and size of chondrocyte cells during the period from 7 to 56 days after birth.

Both the tissue-scale and cell-scale stress concentrations are present and gradually change during development. Using the superposition of the tissue-scale and cell-scale stresses, the peak stress around the chondrocyte cell was evaluated and monitored throughout the development phase. The analysis accounted for the experimentally observed facts, i.e. a stable mineral gradient that exhibits little variations during the development and a gradual shrinkage in size and reduction of the volume fraction of chondrocyte cells.

The axisymmetric cell-scale unit cell shown in Fig. 2 extends from bone to the mineralization front, accounting for grading of the mineral and orthotropic features of the fibrocartilage. Accordingly, the model represents a spherical cell

embedded within the transversely isotropic matrix with the properties varying in the radial direction. The complicated features of the model resulted in the necessity to use a numerical analysis, the results being obtained by COMSOL FEA.

The modeling at the tissue-scale level was conducted by dividing the enthesis into four concentric rings representing the bone, mineralized fibrocartilage, unmineralized fibrocartilage and tendon (see Fig. 2). This model enabled us to analytically evaluate the stress concentration at the tissue scale.

Details of the tissue-scale analysis are presented in [9]. The application of the axisymmetric tissue-scale concentric ring model is justified by the observation that the humeral head is roughly spherical, while tendons form a ring-type structure around it. The concentric ring model was subject to uniform radial stresses assuming plane stress and linearly elastic behavior. While the bone was considered isotropic, the tendon and both mineralized as well as unmineralized sections of the enthesis were transversely isotropic. The exact analytical solution was developed for this model.

2.2 Tissue-scale (global) stress concentration problem

The concentric ring model in Fig. 2 reflects four distinct regions of enthesis present throughout the post-natal development and mature life: (a) tendon, (b) unmineralized fibrocartilage, (c) graded mineralized fibrocartilage, and (d) bone. Interestingly, the size of the graded mineralized fibrocartilage region remains unchanged throughout the development [8]. The concentric ring model was loaded by uniform radial tensile stress to estimate the global stress concentration factor in the structure. The tendon being transversely isotropic, the same constitutive model was adopted for a partially mineralized and unmineralized sections of the fibrocartilage. Without mineralization, the moduli of the tendon are $E_1 = 480$ MPa, $E_2 = 2.28$ MPa; with full mineralization, $E_1 = 1.31E_{\text{bone}}$, $E_2 = 0.84E_{\text{bone}}$, where $E_{\text{bone}} = 20$ GPa. The Poisson's ratio in the transversely plane was assumed to be 0.3, Poisson's ratio in the radial plane was assumed to be 0.1 at all points, which satisfied the positive definiteness constraint of the stiffness tensor. Shear modulus G_{12}

$= 0.008025E_1$, was evaluated using the aspect ratio of collagen fibers $R/L=1/20$ [10].

As is evident, we have to determine the stresses in a system of perfectly bonded orthotropic circular bands, including the isotropic circular core under axisymmetric tensile loading. The radial and tangential components of the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor in the m^{th} orthotropic band due to radial compressive stresses q_m and q_{m-1} applied at the outer and inner interfaces of the m^{th} band, respectively, are [11]:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_r^{(m)}(r) &= \frac{q_{m-1}c_m^{k_m+1}}{1-c_m^{2k_m}} \left[\left(\frac{r}{R_m} \right)^{k_m-1} - \left(\frac{R_m}{r} \right)^{k_m+1} \right] + \\ &\quad \frac{q_m}{1-c_m^{2k_m}} \left[- \left(\frac{r}{R_m} \right)^{k_m-1} + c_m^{2k_m} \left(\frac{R_m}{r} \right)^{k_m+1} \right] \\ \sigma_\theta^{(m)}(r) &= \frac{q_{m-1}c_m^{k_m+1}}{1-c_m^{2k_m}} k_m \left[\left(\frac{r}{R_m} \right)^{k_m-1} + \left(\frac{R_m}{r} \right)^{k_m+1} \right] - \\ &\quad \frac{q_m}{1-c_m^{2k_m}} k_m \left[\left(\frac{r}{R_m} \right)^{k_m-1} + c_m^{2k_m} \left(\frac{R_m}{r} \right)^{k_m+1} \right]\end{aligned}$$

where r is the radial coordinate measured from the center of the bone, $c_m = R_{m-1}/R_m$, R_m and R_{m-1} being the outer and inner radii of the corresponding band, and $k_m = \sqrt{E_\theta^{(m)}/E_r^{(m)}}$. The stress field in the isotropic bone depended only on the stress at its outer boundary, $\sigma_r = \sigma_\theta = -q_0$. As is evident from the previous equations, the stresses can be evaluated if one knows the reaction intensities between the adjacent bands, i.e. q_m .

The continuity requirement for radial displacements along the boundaries of the adjacent bands and along the bone-to-insertion boundary yielded M equations for the M unknown values of q_m :

$$q_o = 2q_1k_1c_1^{k_1-1} \left(\frac{E_\theta^{(1)}}{E_{bone}} (1-\nu_{bone})(1-c_1^{2k_1}) + \left[(1+c_1^{2k_1})k_1 + (1-c_1^{2k_1})\nu_{\theta r}^{(1)} \right] \right)^{-1}$$

$$0 = q_o R_o \alpha_1 + q_1 R_1 \beta_1 + q_2 R_2 \alpha_2$$

$$0 = q_1 R_1 \alpha_2 + q_2 R_2 \beta_2 + q_3 R_3 \alpha_3$$

$$\vdots$$

$$0 = q_{M-2} R_{M-2} \alpha_{M-1} + q_{M-1} R_{M-1} \beta_{M-1} + \sigma_{applied} R_M \alpha_M$$

where $\sigma_{applied} = -p$ is the inward radial stress applied to the outermost boundary of the band of tendon, and the coefficients α_m and β_m are defined in terms of material properties of the bands and geometry in [9]:

$$\alpha_m = \frac{2k_m c_m^{k_m}}{E_\theta^{(m)} (1 - c_m^{2k_m})}$$

$$\beta_m = \frac{1}{E_\theta^{(m)}} \left[\nu_{\theta r}^{(m)} - k_m \frac{(1 + c_m^{2k_m})}{(1 - c_m^{2k_m})} \right] - \frac{1}{E_\theta^{(m+1)}} \left[\nu_{\theta r}^{(m+1)} + k_{m+1} \frac{(1 + c_{m+1}^{2k_{m+1}})}{(1 - c_{m+1}^{2k_{m+1}})} \right]$$

As follows from our experimental observations, during the development the size of the unmineralized region of the enthesis decreases, while that of the mineralized region remains stationary. This observation incorporated in the analytical model briefly described above resulted in the conclusion that the tissue-scale stress slightly decreases during the development.

2.3. Local stress concentration at the cell scale

The local stress concentration analysis utilized the observations of the changes in the post-natal enthesis occurring in the first two months of life. Roughly spherical chondrocyte cells of a radius comparable with the length of the partially mineralized region are present at the early post-natal phase. With time, both the volume fraction and the size of the cells decrease. We suggested that the local stress concentration gradient may be present around these cells. Combining local stresses with those produced

as a result of the stress concentration at the tissue scale may generate sufficiently high stresses to facilitate the process of mineralization. Using the axisymmetric model of a spherical cell embedded within the partially mineralized region we developed a FEA approach to the local analysis. The model cell was embedded at the center of a cylinder whose height twice exceeded the radius (Fig. 2). The cell radius was determined from an experimentally measured area fraction using the Delesse principle [12]. The boundary conditions at the bottom surface of the cylinder reflected symmetry of the model, i.e. the shear stresses were assumed absent. While the vertical displacement of the bottom surface was prevented reflecting high stiffness of the bone, the upper surface was subject to a uniform vertical displacement corresponding to the prescribed axial strain. The side surface of the cylinder was free of tangential stresses and of axial stresses in the vertical direction.

Under the constraints and boundary conditions specified above, the applied vertical stress was found as the vertical reaction force divided by the cylindrical cross sectional area. In turn, the local stress concentration factor was a ratio of the maximum principal stress to the applied vertical stress.

Our experimental data confirmed a reduction in the cell volume fraction during the development period. In particular, while the cells constituted 60% of the volume of the mineralized section of the enthesis seven days after birth, this number dropped to 10% after 56 days. According to our FEA, the local SCF at the cell-matrix interface decreased during this period from 28 to 5.6.

2.4. Total stress amplification during post-natal period

The maximum total stress during the post-natal development period occurs at the equator of the chondrocyte cells as a result of a combination of tissue-scale and local (cell-scale) stress concentrations. This stress is shown in Fig. 3 being normalized with respect to the average peak stress 56 days after birth. Even though the muscle force during the first weeks of life is small, the presence of an extraordinary high local stress concentration

results in high stresses at the cell equators. These stresses are evidently responsible for the formation of mineral in the otherwise underloaded enthesis. It is interesting to note that a high local SCF during the development phase occurs in the enthesis that is graded to reduce global stresses in the tissue connecting tendon and bone.

The tissue-scale stress concentration decreased from about 2.36 at 7 days to about 2.10 at 56 days after birth. The chondrocyte cell volume fraction dropped from 60% to 10% in the same period, while the cell-scale stress concentration factor drastically decreased from 28.0 to 5.5. The combination of tissue-scale and cell-scale stress concentrations at the early development phase resulted in locally elevated stresses, even only 7 days after birth (Fig. 3). Such nearly physiological stress level maintained throughout the development cycle is in line with our hypothesis that the elevated stress environment is paramount for the mineralization of the enthesis.

In view of the above discussion, it is noted that the studies by Hall [13] and Coe et al. [14] shed light on a possible mechanism of the process described above and whose mechanical aspect is evaluated in the study. The local stress concentration seems to facilitate an increase of the size of chondrocytes, inducing a phenotypic change into hypertrophic chondrocytes accompanied by extracellular mineralization. In the contrary, an absence of muscle forces during the development causes a reduced mineralization, improper organization of collagen fibers and vulnerability of enthesis [7], [15].

One of the essential aspects of the micromechanical cell-scale analysis that has not been discussed or considered elsewhere is an exact sequence of the mineral accumulation in the partially mineralized section of enthesis, accounting for the presence of both spherical or spheroidal chondrocyte cells and collagen fibrils. In our previous study we considered the possible sequences of the accumulation of mineral inside and on the surface of the collagen fibril [9], from the front of the mineralized section to the bone. The sequence of bioapatite accumulation during development and the bioapatite distributions within partially mineralized tissues at the insertion are not known [16], but five sequences of mineralization emerge as plausible from the

literature and were analyzed in [9]. All models began with unmineralized collagen fibrils followed by prescribed bioapatite platelet accumulation into gap regions, with the subsequent deposition onto the exterior of collagen fibrils, and within overlap regions. Our results suggest that the pattern of mineralization that exists between tendon and bone may be tailored to maximize the size of a compliant band of tissue in healthy adults. However, it is not presently known how the presence of fibrils in the medium that eventually emerges as a partially mineralized fibrocartilage affects the post-natal accumulation of the mineral and its deposition within the fibrils.

3. Discussion and Conclusions

We demonstrated in the previous work that the graded structure of the enthesis is optimized to achieve an effective load transfer [9], [10]. In the present study, the model of the mouse supraspinatus tendon-to-bone insertion site was followed throughout the post-natal development. It was found that the linear gradient of the mineral content at the insertion site remains stationary throughout the post-natal development. Furthermore, the size of the gradient region does not vary with age, even though the humeral head grows over time.

Our paper examines the effects of mechanical loading on the development of the enthesis over time. We demonstrate that the optimal stress environment facilitating elevated stresses around chondrocyte cells is maintained during the post-natal development as a result of the superposition of two stress concentration effects occurring on a different length scales. Those include the tissue and cell scales that are responsible for tendon macroscopic and local microscopic stress concentrations. As a result, while the chondrocytes shrink and eventually disappear during the post-natal development, mineral develops in the optimum quantity and pattern throughout the enthesis. Apparently, this natural optimized enthesis is not reproduced after injury; the observation that may help explain poor healing outcomes related to high stress environment in healed enthesis reported in [17], [18] and [19]. Results from the current study may also guide a development of the protocols for

tissue-engineered repair of tendon/ligament-to-bone insertion site injuries [20].

In conclusion, the present research elucidates a continuous adaptation of the post-natal enthesis throughout the development where the changes in the size and volume fraction of chondrocyte cells correlate with an elevated nearly physiological stress level conducive for the accumulation of mineral. At the end of the development phase, the enthesis possesses optimum morphology and grading of both the collagen fiber orientation and the mineral distribution resulting in the unsurpassed combination of resiliency, strength and stiffness.

A further work on the subject of the effect of the local stress environment on the development of the enthesis is obviously justified. In particular, our model does not account for the spacing between chondrocyte cells and their mutual interaction. In other words, we consider a single cell in the matrix cylinder in our stress analysis described above, while neglecting the effect of adjacent cells on the local stress concentration factor. Furthermore, we know from the previous research that the collagen fibers change their orientation throughout the length of the insertion site. This aspect is not accounted for in our post-natal modeling due to the lack of sufficient data. It is also not clear why the chondrocyte cells that are present in the unmineralized section of the enthesis do not facilitate the accumulation of mineral in this section. Nevertheless, the result of our experimental and numerical analyses leads to the conclusion that the local stresses at early time points are elevated to near adult physiologic levels, presumably to stimulate chondrocytes mineralization.

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Fig. 1. Moduli of mineralized collagen tissue in the mineralized region at the mature insertion site, normalized with respect to the bone modulus (20 GPa).

Fig. 2. The tissue-scale axisymmetric model of the rotator cuff (left). The section of fibrocartilage adjacent to the bone, including chondrocyte cells (center). The cell-scale model accounting for the local stress concentration is shown on the right.

Fig. 3. The combination of tissue-scale and cell-scale stress concentrations results in the peak stress around the cells that is of the same order as that in the mature organism.